

**Special Issue
“EHMA 2023 Abstract Book”**

Guest Editors: Prof. Sandra C. Buttigieg, MD; Prof. Americo Cicchetti; Prof Axel Kaehne; Dr Alexandre Lourenço; Dr Teppo Heikkilä, MD, EMBA; Prof Todorka Kostadinova; Dr Eszter Kovacs; Prof Federico Lega; Prof Ann Mahon; Dr Rui Dang; Nabil Jamshed MSc MBA BBA; Prof Dr Marija Jevtic, MD; Prof Dr Teresa Magalhães; Prof Dr Henk Nies; Prof Mag Dr Manfred Pferzinger; Prof Dr Rui Santana; Dr Federica Morandi; Mr George Valiotis

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About the EHMA Conference

The EHMA Conference is Europe's preeminent conference on health management. Each year it gathers the full healthcare ecosystem, including health managers and leaders, healthcare professionals, researchers, academics, industry representatives, and decision-makers from Europe, and beyond.

The EHMA Conference provides a platform to discuss the latest health management research, tools and evidence from renowned researchers, academics and professionals. It is concerned on translating research into practice. It creates opportunities for dialogue and exchange on solutions to ensure the sustainability and resilience of health systems.

The EHMA 2023 Annual Conference

EHMA 2023 is the 28th edition of our Annual Conference.

This year's conference theme is 'Health management: sustainable solutions for complex systems'. Three years of the COVID pandemic have exposed gaps and vulnerabilities in European health systems, and the immense pressure on the health and care workforce. Sustainable solutions and strategic thinking are needed to drive the transformation of health systems.

EHMA 2023 is structured around five tracks that reflect the holistic practice of health management, and frame the lenses through which contemporary topics are analysed and discussed.

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) strives for excellent health management for a healthy Europe by supporting the spread of knowledge on effective health management practices. Active since 1982, EHMA exists so that Europe's citizens and communities can benefit from quality, safe, value-based care and health systems.

Our focus is on enhancing the capacity and capabilities of health management to deliver high-quality healthcare and support the successful implementation of health policy. Our commitment is on supporting the provision of data and research findings for evidence-based decision-making and monitoring health policies and practices.

EHMA is the only membership organisation in Europe to bring together the full health management ecosystem, including health and hospital managers, healthcare professionals, researchers, academia, policy and decision-makers. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, and we provide an environment where evidence, challenge and experience are valued and complex debates on current topics can take place.

Urban planning and Public health expertise as a pillar of sustainable solutions in health management

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To achieve inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable cities, one could use synthesis of the challenging relationship between urban planning and Public Health as stated by WHO (2016): “Health is the precondition of urban sustainable development and the first priority for urban planners”.

The “Health in All Policies” strategy, clearly underlines how health depends on the quality of outdoor and indoor living environments. Healthy living and requirements for healthy places, infrastructure for the public good and Public Health, social vulnerability and equality are just a few aspects in a complex matrix when designing the urban spaces for healthy, active and walkable cities.

We should plan and organise healthcare networks having in mind complex circumstances (learnt by pandemic crisis). The concept of the “15 minutes city” as a city of proximity, provides an opportunities to meet the needs for sustainable, fair, quality, healthy living, as well as healthcare. Walkable cities and “15 minutes city” could also increase resilience, pandemic preparedness and help in health crisis management and prevention.

A city of proximity is based on the physical characteristics and people's needs, but also (from a public health perspective) needs in healthcare deliveries. Architects and public health experts in their friendship in expertise insist on long term planning and lessons learnt from COVID pandemic to improve future health care infrastructure.

Improvement of health systems’ sustainability and resilience require strategies, activities and solutions both in infrastructure and health workforce. Learning from the management of pandemic crisis, the localisation of hospitals into the city boundaries, can guarantee both the limitation of flows outside urban areas, containing possible risks of contagion in large high density city centres and the accessibility from the urban areas. Also, different areas must host local facilities able to provide: health services at the primary level, with prevention and health promotion activities.

Sustainable European health systems need to adopt a wide understanding of sustainability considering economic, environmental, and social aspects using urban planning and public health expertise.

Health sector can participate towards achieving the sustainable development goals by respecting the urban health planners’ and public health professionals’ expertise, achieved from the lessons learnt during COVID 19 pandemic, for example.

The hospitals of the future will have to increasingly reflect on its roles, especially towards the most fragile users, and in the same time should increase its own resilient. Urban planning, together with Public health provides sustainable solutions in the management of health sector.